

**New records of *Harpactea srednogora* Dimitrov et Lazarov, 1999
from Bulgaria with a description of the hitherto unknown
female (Aranea: Dysderidae)**

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Abstract. The dysderid spider *Harpactea srednogora* Dimitrov et Lazarov was so far known only by its male sex. The species was found only in a single locality in the Sushtinska Sredna Gora Mountain, Central Bulgaria. New finds from the mountains Vitosha and Western Rhodopes are here reported for the first time, thus extending the species' range in southwestern direction. The unknown female is described and illustrated. The taxonomic affiliations of the species are briefly discussed.

Key words: *Harpactea srednogora*, Western Rhodopes, Vitosha, female description, Bulgaria

Introduction

Only a few species of the spider family Dysderidae occur in Central Europe (PLATNICK, 2007). In Southeastern Europe the family is much richer in species, especially in the countries surrounding the Mediterranean Sea. Some genera in the family, e.g. *Harpactea*, are poorly studied from a taxonomic point of view and one can expect much greater species diversity when more profound investigations are carried out in future, especially on the territory of the Balkan Peninsula. In Bulgaria the genus *Harpactea* is known with 12 species (LAZAROV, 2002). Most of them are hitherto known only from their original descriptions and have never been re-collected since. *Harpactea srednogora* known only by its male found near Panagyurishte in the Sushtinska Sredna Gora Mts. is such a species (cf. DIMITROV & LAZAROV, 1999). Here, I report further finds of the species from the mountains Vitosha and Rhodopes in South Bulgaria, which extend the species' range in south-southwestern direction and change its status of local endemic.

Fig. 1. Distribution map of *Harpactea srednogora*

Material and methods

The material was collected in 2006 through specially designed underground traps. They were made from PVC pipes with diameter of the hole 8 cm and length of 60 or 80 cm. Traps were set in 60 or 80 cm deep holes dug in the soil. The trapping method and all collecting sites will be described elsewhere. The colour is described from ethylenglykol and alcohol preserved specimens. All measurements used in the description are given in mm. The measurements of the legs are taken from the dorsal side (Table 1); body length includes the chelicerae. The epiginae were mounted on a slide in 15% potassium hydroxide (KOH) with their dorsal side up.

Taxonomic part

Harpactea srednogora Dimitrov et Lazarov, 1999

Material examined: **Sushtinska Sredna Gora Mts.**, St. Ivan site near Panagyurishte, 1 male, 1 female, underground traps, GPS: 42°31'004N, 24°11'038E, alt. 584 m, 29.05.-17.06.2006; 1 female, 17.06.-06.08.2006; 1 female, 06.08.-18.11.2006, S. Lazarov leg.; **Vitosha Mts.**, village of Bosnek, near Duhlata cave, 1 female, 4 juveniles, underground traps, GPS: 42°29.755N, 23°11.754E, alt. 992 m, 24.06.-26.08.2006, M. Langourov & N. Simov leg.; 1 male, 2 females, 3 juveniles, 26.08.-03.12.2006, S. Lazarov leg.; above Boyana, Boyanski Kamak Site, 1 male,

Figs 2-6. *H. srednogora*: 2 – epigine, ventral view; 3 – vulva, ventral view; 4 – vulva, dorsal view (Panagyurishte region); 5 – vulva, ventral view; 6 – vulva, dorsal view (Vitosha Mts.) Scale lines: 0.2 mm.

underground traps, 42°38'26,8"N, 23°16'32.1"E, alt. 847 m, 03.06-25.07.2006, B. Petrov leg.; **Western Rhodopes Mts.**, village of Belitsa, Laki Distr., 3 males, 2 females, 7 juveniles, underground traps, 41°50.088N, 24°51.926E, alt. 666 m, 23.04-09.06.2006, 1 female, 09.06-17.07.2006, B. Petrov leg. (Fig. 1).

Description: Female: total length 6.5; cephalothorax: length 3.1, width 4.1; abdomen: length 3.4, width 2.1. Vulva (Figs 2-6). Carapace and chelicerae red-brown, sternum red-orange, abdomen whitish, legs red-orange (Table 1).

Table 1
Leg measurements

Leg	Femur	Patella	Tibia	Metatarsus	Tarsus	Total
I	2.0	1.40	2.3	2.2	0.68	8.58
II	2.6	1.1	2.3	1.9	0.6	8.5
III	1.85	0.7	1.5	1.5	0.65	6.2
IV	2.6	1.15	2.35	2.8	0.8	9.7

Discussion

H. srednogora belongs to the *H. rubicunda* group (cf. DEELEMAN-REINHOLD, 1993). The female is very similar to the other *Harpactea* species, but there are differences in the shape of epigine and vulva (Figs 2-6). The species inhabits screes and dry stony areas covered with bushes and young trees between 584 and 992 m alt. It can be found under stones and deep in the soil.

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**Нови находки на *Harpactea srednogora* Dimitrov et Lazarov, 1999
от България с описание на досега неизвестната женска
(Araneae: Dysderidae)**

Стойан ЛАЗАРОВ

(Резюме)

Паякът *Harpactea srednogora* е известен до момента единствено от типовото му находище в Същинска Средна гора. Само мъжкият пол е описан, тъй като женски екземпляри досега не са намирани. В публикацията се съобщават нови находки на този рядък вид от находища в Западните Родопи, Средна гора и Витоша, което значително разширява ареала му в югозападна посока. Направено е описание и е илюстрирана женската. Таксономичната позиция на вида е дискутирана накратко.